

Supplementary Information to the article:

Palaeontological evidence for community-level decrease in mesopelagic fish size during Pleistocene climate warming in the eastern Mediterranean

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Methodological details

Geochronology

The correlation of the uppermost sampled level (LR>27) to MIS 18 was confirmed by the U^{234}/U^{238} dating of a *Desmophyllum pertusum* coral fragment, which yielded a mean age of 744 Kyr (95% confidence intervals: 616–947 Kyr). The coral fragment was dated using $^{234}U/^{238}U$ radiogenic series at the GEOMAR, Kiel, Germany, following the method of Fietzke et al. (2005). A recent cold-water coral (*D. dianthus*) was used as reference in a standard-sample-standard bracketing approach. $^{234}U/^{238}U$ ages were calculated relative to an initial sea water $^{234}U/^{238}U$ ratio of 1.146 ± 0.002 for the Mediterranean.

Sampling and sample processing

We collected 10.0, 12.7, and 15.1 kg of sediment from levels MIS 20, MIS 19, and MIS 18, respectively. The total amount of sediment required for reconstructing a fish assemblage based on otoliths is at least 10 kg per sample for fine-grained sediments (Agiadi et al., 2018, 2011; Girone et al., 2006; Lin et al., 2019, 2017), and limited outcrop area prevented us from collecting multiple replicate samples of that size. Poorly preserved specimens were left in open nomenclature to reduce the risk of taxonomic error. Specimens unidentified to the species level were included in the analysis, because they are often the only specimens belonging to a given taxon and because their exclusion would result in a bias towards larger and more easily identifiable individuals. Otoliths are generally not expected to occur in fractions smaller than 250 μm (Girone et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2019, 2016; Lombarte et al., 2006; Schwarzahans, 2013). To confirm this, we processed nine sediment samples (~100–250 g each) from the same intervals along the Lardos section using additionally a 125- μm -mesh sieve. No otoliths were found in the fraction below 250 μm . The number of otoliths in each of these samples (fraction > 250 μm) is provided in the supplementary file “replicates”.

The otoliths at each level, found within ~10 kg of sediment, had been deposited on an area of no more than 0.5 m × 0.5 m of the Pleistocene sea bottom. Contrary to scientific survey methods of modern marine environments, such as trawl surveys, the paleontological sampling method allows the capture of small individuals, but large individuals are expected to be rare.

Fish size calculation

Figure S1 shows the length and width measurements on the otoliths. Fish size was estimated from otolith length or, when the length could not be measured due to fragmentation, otolith width using the published transfer functions for the extant species (Table S1). Following Giménez et al. (2016), we preferred power over linear functions for calculating fish length from otolith size when available. In the case of extinct species (here only *Scopelopsis pliocenicus*), specimens that could not be identified to the species level, and species with no information on otolith size–fish size functions, we used averaged coefficients for their closest living relative(s). For broken specimens, we used regression coefficients to determine fish length from otolith width. We used otolith length/width–fish length functions developed for the Mediterranean Sea, whenever possible.

Figure S1 – Sketch of the head of *Ceratoscopelus maderensis* and SEM photograph of one of its otoliths indicating the length (L) and the width (W) measurements.

We used the coefficients of *Bathylagus pacificus* (Hecht, 1987) for the specimens identified as *Bathylagus* sp. For *Callionymus lyra*, the coefficients had been derived from the NE Atlantic (Giménez et al., 2016). For the otoliths identified as Gobiidae indet. and *Gobius* sp., we adopted the otolith length/width–fish length function coefficients of *Gobius* spp. (Giménez et al., 2016) and the averaged fish length–weight coefficients for *Gobius cobitis*, *Gobius cruentatus*, *Gobius niger* and *Gobius paganellus*. The function from the NE Atlantic of *Laemonema laureysi* based on otolith width (Giménez et al., 2016) was applied for specimens assigned to *Laemonema* sp. We used the *Diaphus* spp. otolith length/width–fish length coefficients from NE Atlantic Ocean (Giménez et al., 2016) for the otoliths identified as *Diaphus* spp. and Myctophidae indet. (i.e., indeterminable). The otolith length/width–fish

length coefficients of *Diaphus* spp. (Giménez et al., 2016) and the fish length–weight function of *Scopelopsis multipunctatus* were employed for *Scopelopsis pliocenicus*, as best compromises for this extinct species. The functions of *Pagellus* spp. (Giménez et al., 2016) and the averaged fish length–weight coefficients for *Pagellus acarne*, *P. bogaraveo*, and *P. erythrinus* were used for the otoliths placed under Perciformes indet. We used the otolith length/width–fish length coefficients of *Hygophum* spp. for *H. benoiti* and *H. hygomii*, of *Lobianchia* spp. for *L. dofleini*, and of *Vinciguerria* sp. for *V. poweriae*. We used the coefficients of *Argyropelecus hemigymnus* (Battaglia et al., 2010) for the specimens assigned to *Argyropelecus* sp. The otolith length/width–fish length coefficients of *Gadiculus argenteus* and *Notoscopelus elongatus* were adopted for *Gadiculus thori* and *Notoscopelus kroyeri*, respectively. Otoliths that we were unable to identify to family level due to their poor or incomplete preservation were rare (75 specimens out of 2050 in total, 3.7% of the assemblage) and were excluded from all size analyses.

Fish climatic affinity

For specimens unidentified to the species level, we adopted the climatic-zone affinity of the present-day representatives of the genus, preferring those inhabiting the Mediterranean today, as a conservative solution. However, we excluded from this analysis the specimens placed under Myctophidae indet. These latter specimens may belong to multiple species but could not be identified to the genus and species levels due to their insufficiently good preservation.

Table S1 – Fish length (cm) –weight (g) (*flw*), otolith length–fish length (mm) (*ofl*), and otolith width–fish length (mm) (*ofw*) empirical function parameters *a* and *b* for the identified species. Power functions are in the form of *Fish length* = $a \times \text{otolith length (or otolith width)}^b$, whereas linear functions have the form *Fish length* = $a \times \text{otolith length (or otolith width)}$.

Family	Taxon	<i>a.flw</i>	<i>b.flw</i>	Type.flw	<i>a.ofl</i>	<i>b.ofl</i>	Type.ofl	<i>a.ofw</i>	<i>b.ofw</i>	Type.ofw	Ref
Bathylagidae	<i>Bathylagus</i> sp.	0.00697	3.01	Power	26.85	1.487	Power	NA	NA	NA	Hecht 1987
Bothidae	<i>Arnoglossus laterna</i>	0.00617	3.08	Power	46.83	0.91	Power	64.31	0.92	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Callionymidae	<i>Callionymus lyra</i>	0.01096	2.76	Power	45.59	1.22	Power	107.1	1.29	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Clupeidae	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.00708	3.05	Power	55.75	0.95	Power	101.78	1.17	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Gadidae	<i>Gadiculus argenteus</i>	0.00676	3.07	Power	19.47	0.89	Power	31.68	0.79	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Gadidae	<i>Gadiculus thori</i>	0.00813	2.09	Power	19.47	0.89	Power	31.68	0.79	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Gobiidae	<i>Deltentosteus quadrimaculatus</i>	0.00759	3.09	Power	26.33	0.92	Power	27.87	1.04	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Gobiidae	<i>Gobiidae</i> indet.	0.00929	3.075	Power	29.06	0.94	Power	41.09	0.84	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius</i> sp.	0.00929	3.075	Power	29.06	0.94	Power	41.09	0.84	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Macrouridae	<i>Caelorinchus caelorhincus</i>	0.00275	3.13	Power	3.8	1.24	Power	1.58	2.07	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Macrouridae	<i>Nezumia aequalis</i>	0.00245	3.09	Power	5.25	1.09	Power	4.95	1.42	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Modidae	<i>Laemonema</i> sp.	0.00457	3.13	Power	3.8	1.87	Power	37.78	1.52	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Benthoosema glaciale</i>	0.1023	3.1	Power	37.97	1.3	Power	30.71	1.21	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Ceratoscopelus maderensis</i>	0.00501	3.14	Power	32.3	0.71	Power	42.28	0.84	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus holti</i>	0.00955	3.2	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus rafinesquii</i>	0.0049	3.07	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus</i> sp.	0.00775	3.03	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus taaningi</i>	0.00955	3.02	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Electrona risso</i>	0.00389	3.12	Power	13.44	2.18	Linear	12.54	1.846	Linear	Battaglia et al. 2010
Myctophidae	<i>Hygophum benoiti</i>	0.01023	3.1	Power	34.98	0.49	Power	35.32	0.51	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Hygophum hygomii</i>	0.01023	3.1	Power	34.98	0.49	Power	35.32	0.51	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Lampanyctus crocodilus</i>	0.00525	3.12	Power	59.99	0.73	Power	57.71	0.89	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Lobianchia dofleini</i>	0.00955	3.02	Power	17.62	0.86	Power	20.8	0.89	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016

Family	Taxon	<i>a.flw</i>	<i>b.flw</i>	Type.flw	<i>a.ofl</i>	<i>b.ofl</i>	Type.ofl	<i>a.ofw</i>	<i>b.ofw</i>	Type.ofw	Ref
Myctophidae	<i>Myctophidae</i> indet.	0.00775	3.03	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Myctophum punctatum</i>	0.00389	3.12	Power	15.1	1.35	Power	20.85	1.24	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	0.00562	3.09	Power	22.5	0.94	Power	35.91	1	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Notoscopelus kroyeri</i>	0.00457	3.09	Power	22.5	0.94	Power	35.91	1	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Myctophidae	<i>Scopelopsis pliocenicus</i>	0.00457	3.09	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Phosichthyidae	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	0.00933	3.09	Power	36.06	0.52	Power	42.76	0.5	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Phycidae	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.00468	3.13	Power	4.4	1.73	Linear	17.81	1.95	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Sparidae	<i>Perciformes</i> indet.	0.0109	3.03	Power	23.91	1.07	Power	54.38	0.85	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016
Sternoptychidae	<i>Argyropelecus</i> sp.	0.01558	3.052	Power	70.7	-5.998	Linear	45.99	-3.172	Linear	Battaglia et al. 2010
Sternoptychidae	<i>Maurolicus muelleri</i>	0.00457	3.17	Power	24.768	-2.493	Linear	30.47	-1.832	Linear	Battaglia et al. 2010
Indet.	Indet.	0.00775	3.03	Power	20.08	0.9	Power	27.8	0.8	Power	Gimenez et al. 2016

Table S2 –Climatic-zone affinities from AquaMaps (Kaschner et al., 2016) and habitats from Fishbase (Froese and Pauly, 2020) for the identified taxa. Tr: Tropical; ST: Subtropical; Te: Temperate; SP: Subpolar.

Family	Taxon	Habitat	Climatic affinity			
			Tr	ST	Te	SP
Bathylagidae	<i>Bathylagus</i> sp.	pelagic	0	0	1	0
Bothidae	<i>Arnoglossus laterna</i>	demersal	0	1	0	0
Callionymidae	<i>Callionymus lyra</i>	demersal	0	0	1	0
Clupeidae	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Gadidae	<i>Gadiculus argenteus</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	0
Gadidae	<i>Gadiculus thori</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	1
Gobiidae	<i>Deltentosteus quadrimaculatus</i>	demersal	0	1	0	0
Gobiidae	Gobiidae indet.	demersal	0	1	0	0
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius</i> sp.	demersal	0	1	0	0
Macrouridae	<i>Caelorinchus caelorhincus</i>	demersal	1	1	0	0
Macrouridae	<i>Nezumia aequalis</i>	demersal	1	1	0	0
Modidae	<i>Laemonema</i> sp.	demersal	1	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Benthoosema glaciale</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	1
Myctophidae	<i>Ceratoscopelus maderensis</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	0
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus holti</i>	pelagic	1	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus rafinesquii</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus</i> sp.	pelagic	1	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Diaphus taaningi</i>	pelagic	1	0	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Electrona risso</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	0
Myctophidae	<i>Hygophum benoiti</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	0
Myctophidae	<i>Hygophum hygomii</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Lampanyctus crocodilus</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Lobianchia dofleini</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Myctophidae	Myctophidae indet.	pelagic	1	1	1	0
Myctophidae	<i>Myctophum punctatum</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Myctophidae	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	0
Myctophidae	<i>Notoscopelus kroyeri</i>	pelagic	0	0	0	1
Myctophidae	<i>Scopelopsis pliocenicus</i>	pelagic	1	0	0	0
Phosichthyidae	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Phycidae	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	demersal	0	0	1	0
Sparidae	Perciformes indet.	demersal	0	1	0	0
Sternoptychidae	<i>Argyropelecus</i> sp.	pelagic	0	1	0	0
Sternoptychidae	<i>Maurollicus muelleri</i>	pelagic	0	0	1	0
indet.	indet.	pelagic	1	1	1	0

Additional Results

Table S3 – Summary of the otolith size–fish size results

Descriptor	MIS 20	MIS 19	MIS 18
Number of all otoliths	710	1037	303
Number of indetermined otoliths	55	0	20
Number of taxa	20	24	21
Number of species	15	19	17
Number with size estimate	655	1022	283
Proportion with size estimate	100	98.55	100
Mean length (cm)	3.55	3.12	3.57
Median length (cm)	3.43	3.04	3.39
Min length (cm)	1.04	0.83	1.37
Max length (cm)	24.52	10.07	10.01
Mean weight (g)	0.77	0.42	0.82
Median weight (g)	0.36	0.29	0.40
Min weight (g)	0.01	0.002	0.02
Max weight (g)	106.13	29.25	23.37

Figure S2 – Fish assemblage composition in MIS 20, MIS 19, and MIS 18. A. Relative abundances of the families; B. Relative abundances of the dominant species.

Figure S3 – Fish length (A) and weight (B) frequency distributions during MIS 20 (glacial), MIS 19 (interglacial), and MIS 18 (glacial). The median fish size at the assemblage level is smaller during the MIS19 interglacial.

Table S4 – Absolute abundances of the different taxa in the assemblages and median weights of the individual species.

Taxon	Absolute abundance			Median weight (g)		
	MIS 20	MIS 19	MIS 18	MIS 20	MIS 19	MIS 18
<i>Myctophidae</i> indet.	162	398	59	-	-	-
<i>Hygophum benoiti</i>	190	139	67	0.54	0.57	0.49
<i>Diaphus</i> sp.	65	183	49	-	-	-
<i>Ceratoscopelus maderensis</i>	142	97	30	0.34	0.44	0.61
<i>Lobianchia dofleini</i>	21	60	7	0.23	0.26	0.23
<i>Diaphus taaningi</i>	9	31	1	0.34	0.38	0.45
<i>Gadiculus argenteus</i>	9	17	7	0.60	2.24	0.30
<i>Lampanyctus crocodilus</i>	19	7	5	1.36	1.93	1.11
<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	6	0	18	1.31	-	1.07
<i>Diaphus holti</i>	8	8	6	0.17	0.35	0.28
<i>Hygophum hygomii</i>	2	17	0	2.31	0.99	-
<i>Myctophum punctatum</i>	7	10	1	0.51	0.18	0.20
<i>Benthoosema glaciale</i>	2	7	5	3.29	5.54	16.98
<i>Gobius</i> sp.	2	2	10	-	-	-
<i>Diaphus rafinesquii</i>	2	9	1	0.51	0.22	0.73
<i>Maurolicus muelleri</i>	0	12	0	-	0.24	-
<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	3	0	6	1.66	-	0.61
<i>Scopelopsis pliocenicus</i>	0	8	0	-	0.17	-
<i>Callionymus lyra</i>	1	0	5	4.37	-	3.16
<i>Electrona risso</i>	0	5	0	-	0.10	-
<i>Deltentosteus quadrimaculatus</i>	2	0	2	0.41	-	0.31
<i>Caelorinchus caelorhincus</i>	0	3	0	-	0.002	-
<i>Notoscopelus kroyeri</i>	0	3	0	-	0.65	-
<i>Laemonema</i> sp.	2	0	0	34.50	-	-
<i>Nezumia aequalis</i>	0	2	0	-	0.31	-
<i>Phycis bleunoides</i>	0	1	1	-	0.04	0.36
<i>Argyropelecus</i> sp.	0	1	0	-	1.44	-
<i>Arnoglossus laterna</i>	0	0	1	-	-	5.71
<i>Bathylagus</i> sp.	1	0	0	106.13	-	-
<i>Gadiculus thori</i>	0	0	1	-	-	0.66
Gobiidae indet.	0	1	0	-	-	-
Perciformes indet.	0	0	1	-	-	-
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0	1	0	-	1.76	-

Figure S4 – Changes in fish weight by family across the studied MIS 20–18 glacial–interglacial–glacial interval. The number of specimens with weight estimate in each time interval is shown above the boxplots; numbers in green are the median values.

Figure S5 – Changes in relative abundance compared to median weight of each species from MIS 20 to MIS 19, and from MIS 19 to MIS 18. The dashed line indicates lack of change in relative abundance. The black square corresponds to all myctophids combined. Most of the changes in the assemblages composition are due to shifts in the abundance of myctophids.

Otolith preservation

To test for potential differences in otolith preservation between the three studied samples, we assigned scores, on a scale from 0 (excellent) to 3 (poor), to six alteration variables, for each otolith, following the protocol of Agiadi et al. (2021): completeness, translucency, bioerosion, edge preservation, dissolution and ornamentation loss (Table S5). Completeness reflects the level of fragmentation of the otolith. Translucency varies from almost fully translucent in pristine otoliths, to opaque and colored in very altered otoliths. Bioerosion is due to the activity of microborers (mainly algae, fungi, and sponges). Edge preservation reflects the degree of erosion or chipping of the periphery of the otolith. Dissolution gives a chalky or grainy appearance and dense pitting of the otolith surface. Ornamentation loss indicates the preservation of the morphology of the otolith inner face. We compared the preservation of the otoliths found in the three beds in terms of their average taphonomic scores using Kruskal-Wallis testing individual taphonomic parameters.

Table S5 – Taphonomic variables and explanation of the scoring. Note that the translucency scoring has been modified from Agiadi et al. (2021) in order to better reflect the range of alteration of this characteristic in fossil otoliths, as compared to the younger specimens examined by these authors.

Taphonomic variable	Possible values			
Completeness	0 = 95–100% complete	1 = 75–95% complete	2 = 50–75% complete	3 = 25–50% complete
Translucency	0 = clear, translucent	1 = white, not translucent	2 = yellow, not translucent	3 = dark yellow/orange/brown, not translucent
Bioerosion	0 = no bioerosion	1 = 1/3 bioeroded	2 = 2/3 bioeroded	3 = more than 2/3 bioeroded
Edge preservation	0 = sharp, pristine	1 = 1/3 eroded/chipped	2 = 2/3 eroded/chipped	3 = more than 2/3 eroded/chipped
Dissolution	0 = absent	1 = patchy dissolution	2 = extensive dissolution	3 = predominately dissolved
Ornamentation loss	0 = pristine ornamentation	1 = more than 50% of ornamentation preserved	2 = ornamentation traces	3 = almost all ornamentation lost

Figure S6 – Average taphonomic scores of the otoliths in the three intervals.

Figure S7 – Otolith preservation in the three sampled levels MIS 20, MIS 19, MIS 18, based on six taphonomic variables (completeness, translucency, bioerosion, edge preservation, dissolution, and ornamentation loss).

Although the state of individual specimens can vary from pristine to highly degraded, the overall preservation is good, and the average taphonomic score of the otoliths in the three sampled intervals does not differ significantly (Kruskal-Wallis test $\chi^2 = 0.537$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.765$; Figure S5). In terms of the individual taphonomic variables (Figure S6, Table S6), the degree of fragmentation and bioerosion increases in MIS 19, which may explain the higher number of broken otoliths (16 specimens) that we were unable to measure. In addition, the degree of edge preservation is lower in MIS 20 than in MIS 19 and MIS 18, which may have led to the overall underestimated measurements of otolith length, although we do not expect these to be significant. This is because only 12% of the otoliths are very altered in terms of edge preservation in MIS 20 compared to 8% in MIS 19 and 5% in MIS 18 (Figure S6).

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